

Proceedings

Committee on Sustainability
cilect.org/committee/scs/

CILECT Congress 2025 - Guadalajara

October 28 + 29, 2025

CC BY-SA 4.0

Introduction

Members of the Committee

Larry Engel - American University - USA

Gerda Cammaer - Toronto Metropolitan University (TMU) - Canada

Frode Søbstad - Kristiania University of Applied Sciences (KUC) - Norway

Tobias Frühmorgen - Universidade Lusófona Lisbon - Portugal

Aurora Ojeda Coronado - Escuela Nacional de Artes Cinematográficas (ENAC) - Mexico

Kenneth Kaplan - Witwatersrand University (WSOA) - South Africa

David Balfour - Victorian College of the Arts (VCA) - Australia

Introduction

SCS pursues four main objectives:

To foster the green agenda across the association and its implications for film education and production

To design and promote initiatives for green production education across member schools

To produce concrete guidelines for the integration of the green production agenda in member schools

To incentivize students' productions that embed "green" values

Agenda

Day 1

- Introduction and Green Survey
- 20 Ideas for Sustainable Film Production
- Agents of Change
- Green Library
- Case Study
- – let's hear from you

Day 2

- Recap from Day 1
- Carbon Calculators
- Green Tools
- Classroom Examples
- Manifesto
- – let's hear from you

How green are we so far?

Brief overview current sustainability practices at CILECT schools
= Based on Preliminary results of the survey

Call for participation: We need your input!

our SURVEY

tally.so/r/w4OWXY

20 Ideas for a Sustainable Film Production

CILECT - Standing Committee on Sustainability (SCS)

Tobias Frühmorgen, Lusófona University / FilmEU

October 2025

doi.org/10.60543/8zhv-h514

20 Ideas for Sustainable Film Production

WHY: Bringing sustainability or green practices into filmmaking and teaching does not need a lot of technology or money. These 20 ideas provide a starting point for going green in your school, with your students.

WHAT: This slide deck describes basic actions to reduce your environmental impact during production. Like a plant, let it grow organically at your school.

HOW: Start with this slide deck in your classes. Open discussion and build a community around green thinking. Add your ideas too.

Sustainability is different in each country. Try to do the best you can.

20 Ideas for Sustainable Film Production

Target Group:

Teachers in Cinema, Fiction,
Animation, and Documentary.
Students.

Leaders of film schools.
Administrative staff.

1. Buy-in

- ○ ○ ○
- ○ ○ ○
- ○ ○ ○
- ○ ○ ○

Going green is a team effort. Everyone can learn about sustainability and commit to minimizing the environmental impact of filmmaking. There may be a sustainability coordinator assigned when there is a large crew. Start in pre-production.

Start easy. Don't force anyone.

2. Communication

Don't argue about climate change. It won't help convince people.

Argue with budget, not with ideology.

Argue with: efficiency.

Argue with: more time for creativity.

Don't force anyone.

Don't say: "you have to".

3. Transport

Use public transport to go to school
Use a bike to go to school. Check if your city offers a bike renting system.
Avoid Taxis/Ubers/Bolts.
Prefer train/bus over flights.
Spend time on trains instead of cars.
Don't drive alone. Take other people on board.

4. Single Use Products

-
-
-
-
-
-
-
-
-
-
-
-
-
-
-
-
-
-
-
-

Avoid using single-use products.
Avoid using plastic bottles, no plastic bags,
no throw-away food containers.
Refuse to use them if you're asked.
Recycle them if you must use them.

5. Garbage & Recycling

Provide clearly labelled bins
(glass/paper/plastic/trash) with picture.
Choose recycling colors that are used in
your country.
Position them where waste is generated.

6. Electricity

- Use the electric grid instead of generators.
- Switch to a green energy provider
- Use the generator only if the grid is farther than 150 meters away.
- Use solar-powered or rechargeable generators if possible.

7. Water

Ask the team to bring named water bottles/
canteens/cups.

Avoid one-time-use plastic bottles.

Provide large water dispensers for refilling.

8. Food

Try: One vegetarian day per week or shoot day.
Alternative: Ask the crew to opt-in for meat.

9. Paper

Avoid printing on paper unless really needed.
Use recycled paper.
Use digital tools instead.

10. Batteries

Use rechargeable batteries (that's easy).

11. Unplug

Switch off devices overnight.
Switch off devices on weekends.
Switch off devices during holidays.
Avoid sleep-mode.

12. Costumes

X X X X
X X X X
X X X X
X X X X

Reuse, rent, borrow, or buy second-hand clothes.
Avoid fast-fashion.

13. Set and Props

Avoid buying new every time.

Reduce, Reuse, Renew, Recycle.

Create or join a school “materials exchange” to share.

Create a room at the school for keeping costumes and props.

Accept donations.

Share with other projects.

14. Equipment Lifecycle

Maintain and repair before replacing and throwing away.
Share gear across classes via booking systems.
Buy higher quality products with longer life-cycles.
Avoid buying cheap stuff. You will probably buy it twice.

15. Lights

Use LED lights, bounces, and reflectors.
Schedule to make use of daylight.
Check: Is the night shoot really necessary?
Switch off or dim between takes and pauses.

16. Footprint of Data

Local data first. Not everything needs to be on the cloud.
Local hard drives are much cheaper than the cloud.
Use storage providers with e2e-encryption and green energy.
Only store proxies on the cloud.
Edit with proxies.
Use efficient codecs (h.265/AV1) for export.
Compress big PDFs into smaller ones before sending.

17. Campus

Check if your institution/campus/cafeteria uses garbage separation

Ask why not and what is needed to start.

Check when rooms are overheated or overcooled

Ask for a 1–2-degree adjustment.

Reducing by 1°C (1.8°F) saves 5-10% of energy.

18. Locations

Choose nearby locations. (This also reduces the budget.)
Set a reasonable “local radius” for student projects.
Cluster scenes across projects to reduce team moves.

19. Nature

When shooting on ancestral lands or in natural parks:
Respect nature by leaving no trace of your filming
except your footprints.

20. Diversity in Content and Team

Encourage the representation of diverse cultures, identities, and perspectives in scripts and productions.

Ensure that the production team reflects a variety of cultural backgrounds, genders, and orientations.

Offer workshops and mentorships for underrepresented groups.

Collaborate with community organizations to tell authentic and meaningful stories that represent diverse voices.

Evaluate and adjust hiring and casting processes to ensure equal opportunities for all team members and actors.

Incorporate inclusive practices on set. Every voice is heard and valued. Diversity is respected.

Remember that change takes time.

This is a publication of the CILECT Standing Committee on Sustainability (SCS)
October 2025 #2
cilect.org/committee/scs/

Contact:

Larry Engel | engel@american.edu

Tobias Frühmorgen | tobias.fruhmorgen@ulusofona.pt

Agents of Change

WHY: Film students already live in a climate-changed world — they feel anxiety, urgency, and responsibility.

WHAT: This section asks how we, as educators, can empower them to turn that lived reality into meaningful stories across every genre.

HOW: By framing students as agents of change — not preaching, but embedding, weaving, modelling, and situating climate within their creative voice.

The climate crisis is already shaping their future. Cinema should not stay silent.

Silent on Climate

Climate barely exists in film and TV storytelling — and students are inheriting that silence.

Agents of Change - Provocation

- If audiences are asking for climate stories, why aren't we equipping students to tell them?
- If students are already living with climate anxiety, why doesn't it appear in their films?
- If cinema shapes the cultural imagination, what does our silence teach?

Challenge

Students live in a climate-shaped world – but struggle to put it on screen.

Audiences want it – but rarely see it.

So how do we help students:

- Express lived reality without preaching?
- Embed climate meaningfully across any genre?
- Weave it into story worlds, rather than bolt it on?
- Model character actions and consequences?
- Situate their work along a spectrum of engagement?

This is not about forcing a message – it's about teaching narrative literacy for the world they are inheriting.

The Climate Story Spectrum (for Educators)

How we might scaffold student agency without forcing a single mode of engagement

Level	How climate appears	Why it matters (for learning & impact)	
1. Climate Placement	Sustainable behaviors or environmental elements appear in design, props, or character choices without comment.	Normalises climate-conscious living; shows students they can integrate climate subtly without changing genre or plot focus.	
2. Climate Mention	Characters refer to climate change or related emotional states (anxiety, policy, weather) in passing.	Validates what students and audiences already feel; gives permission to name the issue without making it “about” climate.	
3. Climate World	The story world shows the effects of climate change (storms, resource shifts, migrations), shaping context but not driving the main plot.	Encourages students to explore intersectionality — climate as part of economics, identity, conflict, community.	
4. Climate Characters	Characters and plot are directly motivated by climate crisis and its consequences.	Enables deep emotional and narrative engagement; builds agency and activism through story arcs.	

Agents of Change

FRAME	Key Purpose (For Students)	
Represent – don't preach	Express climate through lived emotional reality rather than messaging.	
Embed – don't bolt on	Let climate shape the background logic of the world or situation.	
Weave – make it part of the story fabric	Allow climate to influence conflict, relationships, or genre energy.	
Model – show choices and consequences	Reveal character values through action, not slogans.	
Situate – place your story on the climate spectrum	Help students consciously choose their level of engagement.	

Agents of Change - Resources

Industry Guides & Storytelling Initiatives

Good Energy – Storytelling resource supporting climate-positive narratives

<https://www.goodenergystories.com/>

We Are Albert (BAFTA) – Climate content hub and sustainability standards for production

<https://wearealbert.org/climate-content/>

Planet Placement – Editorial hub for integrating climate themes on screen

<https://planetplacement.co.uk>

Rewrite the Future (NRDC) – Climate storytelling program for film and TV creators

<https://www.nrdc.org/RewriteTheFuture>

Sustainable Production Frameworks & Tools

Sustainable Screens Australia – Tools, resources, and production sustainability guidelines

<https://www.sustainablescreens.au/tools-resources>

Carbon'Clap (Ecoprod) – Carbon calculator for film, TV, and advertising production

<http://www.carbonclap.ecoprod.com>

Sustainable Entertainment Alliance – International coalition promoting eco-conscious entertainment practices

<https://www.sustainableentertainmentalliance.org/>

Green Library

jottacloud.com/s/42446df608cb2c84e22b1c2b0cc69995658/list

2 parts:

1. Theoretical Research
2. Practical Implementation

Three Major themes:

1. Environmental Impact of Media
2. Media's own Role in Ecological Crises and Solutions
3. Environmental storytelling

Green Library

Theoretical Impact

- a. Environmental Impact of Media
- b. Media's own Role in Ecological Crises and Solutions
- c. Environmental storytelling

Green Library

Practical Examples and Tools

Online Tools, Handbooks from around the world, Whitepapers and Other Sources ...

jottacloud.com/s/42446df608cb2c84e22b1c2b0cc69995658/list

Green Library

1. Environmental Impact of Media

Green Library

2. Media's own role in the Ecological Crisis and Solutions

Green Library

3. Environmental Storytelling

4. Practical Examples and various Online Tools

Creative Climate Tools & E-Learning

4. Practical Examples and various Online Tools

CTRL Faculty Resources
A unit of the *Office of the Provost*

[Home](#) | [Services](#) | [Resources](#) | [Programs & Events](#) | [Calendar](#) | [About](#)

GREEN TIPS AND RESOURCES

Innovative Tips and Ideas from AU's Green Teachers = American University (Washington)

4. Practical Examples and various Online Tools

By Film Industry Organizations

ALBERT Climate Content Production Articles Toolkit Academy Suppliers

We are the home of environmental sustainability for the screen industries. This is the place to share, learn and act on our impact.

PGW Green
PRODUCERS GUILD OF AMERICA

Unified Best Practices Guide

Green Producers Club

The Green Producers Tool

4. Practical Examples and various Online Tools

Carbon Calculators

The image shows a screenshot of the Film Carbon Calculator website. The top navigation bar is dark with white text for the menu items: CHALLENGE, SOLUTION, HOW IT WORKS, KEY BENEFITS, and CONTACT US. On the left side of the navigation bar is the 'fcc' logo, which includes a stylized leaf and a calculator icon, with the text 'FILM CARBON CALCULATOR' underneath. The main content area features a dark background with a silhouette of a person operating a camera. Overlaid on this image is the text: 'Film Carbon Calculator', 'Environmental and', and 'Sustainability Reporting'.

4. Practical Examples and various Online Tools

The image shows the homepage of the Green Film website. At the top left is the 'GREEN FILM' logo. The navigation menu includes 'Certify Your Film', 'Films', 'GF Research Lab', 'News', and 'Partners'. A prominent green button labeled 'DOWNLOAD RATING SYSTEM' is located in the top right. Language options 'EN IT ES' are also visible. The main content area features the text 'Rating Systems' in green, followed by the 'GREEN FILM' logo and the headline 'Rating system and certification for a sustainable film production.' The background is a dark green space with a large, stylized globe illustration. The globe is divided into sections showing various film production activities: a person on a ladder with a light, a person operating a camera on a tripod, a person at a desk, and a person in a suit. The globe is surrounded by stars and clouds.

GREEN FILM

Rating system and certification
for a sustainable film production.

4. Practical Examples and various Online Tools

Scope 1 & 2 Emissions in Film and Television Production

July 2025

Your Suggestions or Ideas?

= 2 Whitepapers:
(Sustainable Entertainment Alliance
& Sustainable Production Alliance
(ALBERT / BAFTA))

CLOSE UP:

**Scope 3 Emissions in
Film and Television
Production**

Green Toolbox

Calculators

Certifications Systems

Country Profiles

Case Studies

Trainings

Green Manager Course

crescine.eu/green-toolbox

crescine

Ecosystem Profiles

Croatia

Denmark

Estonia

Flanders

Ireland

Lithuania

Portugal

Compare Ecosystems

| Territory | |
|---|---|---|---|---|---|---|---|
| Green Production Guide | |
| Legislation | |
| Funding, Consultants, Sustainability Officers | |
| Green Education | |
| Co-Production Criteria | |
| Prospects / Plans | |

Carbon Calculators

CarbonClap

Carbon'Clap is Ecoprod's free carbon calculator designed to measure greenhouse-gas emissions from audiovisual, film, TV, and advertising productions. Originally launched in 2012 and overhauled in 2022-2023, it updates methodologies and user experience in collaboration with industry stakeholders and environmental experts. The tool supports live-action, animation (2D/3D), and post-production scopes, provides activity-data entry across key departments (e.g., energy, travel, set construction, catering), and generates results aligned with French CNC certification criteria; it also enables Excel exports of activity data to match CNC impact-measurement requirements. Carbon'Clap is positioned to facilitate comparable

COUNTRY:

ORIGINATOR:

EcoProd

The Green Producers Tool

The Green Producers Tool is a carbon-emissions measurement platform designed for cultural and creative productions, including Film & TV, Festivals, Performing Arts, Events, Sports, and Exhibitions/Artworks, with a museum-focused module in development. It enables users—producers, purchasers, and suppliers—to plan scenarios, collect activity data (e.g., travel, food, equipment use, waste), and generate reports showing CO₂e totals by activity, category, and overall production. Accessible on desktop and as a mobile web app, the tool supports on-the-go data entry during production. It includes more than 12,000 emission factors and is updated in consultation with members

COUNTRY:

ORIGINATOR:

Green Producers Club

Certification Systems

Green Film

Trentino Film Commissions 'Green Film' is one of the most used certification systems for film and tv- productions.

COUNTRY:

ORIGINATOR:

Green Film/
Trentino Film
Commission

EcoProd Label

The Ecoprod Label aims to highlight audiovisual projects distinguished by their ambitious environmental initiatives and actions. It's a complete, free reference tool to reduce the environmental impact of your production.

COUNTRY:

ORIGINATOR:

EcoProd

Austrian Ecolabel

The Austrian Ecolabel is a certificate given to Austrian film productions, not to the film production companies. The guideline includes criteria in the fields of mobility and climate protection, set, materials for buildings and props, costumes and make-up, technology,

COUNTRY:

Green Motion

The GreenMotion label represents the nationwide ecological standards for audiovisual production in Germany, developed by the Green Shooting Working Group, which includes major German TV broadcasters, VoD services, film/TV production companies, and associations.

COUNTRY:

ORIGINATOR:

"Green
Shooting" work

crescine.eu/green-toolbox

Green Storage Providers

Criteria:

- Green Energy
- Privacy Laws
- e2e-encrypted

Jottacloud (NO)

Koofr (SK/DE)

Infomaniak kDrive (CH)

.. more?

SOME THINGS THAT ARE NOT IN
THE MANUAL

(SOSTAINABILITY MANUAL*)

ENAC-UNAM Case Study
CILECT 2025

First a clarification.

In Spanish, we use two concepts: Sustainability with an O, which has no translation into English and is the broad concept that seeks a balance between environmental, economic, and social aspects for long-term development, while sustainability with a U focuses more on the preservation and rational use of natural resources, ensuring that ecosystems are not depleted or damaged.

In Mexico, sometimes sustainability feels like a Scandinavian luxury. They have electric trains and bicycles to reach their destinations.

And here we get
energy with atole,
tamales....

And here we get energy with atole, tamales....

styrofoam.

plastic

...and a lot of
creativity.

This presentation is about
what we've learned while
trying to make cinema —
and life — more
sustainable

EARTH HOUR

Context

At our school, we train incredible filmmakers: experts in camera, sound and script....

...BUT

who don't know how to get rid of trash...

...among other things.

We realized that we often lack something:
awareness about how to live s**O**stainably.

It's not just about making films, but about being
responsible global citizens.

SHOT

COUNTER SHOT

THAT'S WHY WE
DECIDED TO CREATE
A DIFFERENT KIND
OF MANUAL.

IT'S NOT A FILM
MANUAL, BUT A
LIFE MANUAL FOR
FILMMAKERS WHO

WANT TO MAKE A
DIFFERENCE.

FILM SHOULD BE AN
INSTRUMENT OF PEACE,
EMPATHY, AND AWARENESS,
WHICH MEANS IT SHOULD BE
ENVIRONMENTALLY FRIENDLY
AND STEEPED IN SOCIAL
RESPONSIBILITY.

Social Responsibility

Citizens of the world

Global awareness, cinema is very powerful and the earth is in danger, therefore, we have the responsibility to be “Citizens of the world” with a deep understanding and respect of the cultures, stories and trends of our planet and we are developing the ability to tell stories that resonate in otherness.

We have a **sustainable** philosophy as a way of life, social and environmental awareness, sensitivity and commitment to the creation of content that provokes meaningful reflections and promotes positive, inclusive, sustainable and peaceful change.

We are all equal human beings, we do not even question gender equality, so we are empathetic people and we work for peace and not for confrontation, we are communicators.

Social Responsibility

Citizens of the world

TRANSVERSAL TEACHING

THREADS FROM THE
SUSTAINABILITY
MANUAL

Threads

1 Sustainability & environment

2 Physical and mental wellbeing

3 Soft skills & gender perspective

4 Learning to learn

Thread number 1 is what brings us here.

1 Sustainability & environment

EL Reciclación

We started with a project called the Recycling Marathon.

The idea was simple: collect PET, cans, and glass, sell them, and use the money to buy Rechargeable batteries and consumables for filmmaking. Families could support with recyclable materials instead of money. It worked, but six months later, Mexico declared the Circular Economy. Now, those who previously bought our recyclables charge us to collect them. In

theory, this is great because while it won't be so easy to raise money, simply reducing and separating waste to ensure proper management could gradually turn us into true global citizens.

At least we're starting to discuss the issue, and while the transition won't be easy, young people are very receptive, concerned, and responsible for taking action.

Sustainability Paradoxes

To reflect

Living sustainably in Latin America, and I'm pretty sure it's similar in Africa, is actually more expensive.

Compostable materials can cost +-ten times more than styrofoam. Fresh fruits and vegetables are pricier than processed food and bottled soft drinks. So, sustainability becomes a privilege, when it should be a right — and a shared responsibility.

Charola Termica Reyma 835 500 Pzs (10paq/50pzs) Desechable
Por TONA EMPAQUES

\$ 577

24 meses de \$ 34.87

Berry Green 50 Contenedores Compostables
Grandes Para Alimentos, Material de Alta Calidad,
Resistente a los Liquidos, Ecológico, Hecho de Fibras
de Caña de Azúcar 20.5 x 20.5 x 6.5 cm (8 Pulgadas)
Visita la tienda de BERRY GREEN
4.5 ★★★★★ 55 calificaciones
Opción Amazon
50+ comprados el mes pasado

\$312⁰⁰
\$31.66 x12 meses Ver planes

Pagos y Seguridad 30 días de devolución sin costo Enviado por Amazon

Marca BERRY GREEN
Color Café
Material Bagazo
Característica del material Compostable
Dimensiones del producto 20,3l. x 20,3an. x 6alt. centimeters

...BUT

Small Steps, Big Lessons

After a year of persistence and awareness, we achieved small but significant changes: Young people no longer eat in disposable containers and cook their own food, no more junk food.

Small Steps, Big Lessons

We have an active worm compost Bins for intimate waste, PET collection point on campus.

They may seem like minor things, but for our students, it's the beginning of a new environmental awareness and an embedded philosophy of sOustainable living.

Learnings

Cinema can change habits.

Students can become agents of peace and sustainability.

Low budgets often mean high creativity.

We recycle ideas, locations, and sometimes even actors.

That's the beauty of filmmaking in Latin America.

Thank you

Cinema is beautiful and can be sustainable, and while it's easier to find Styrofoam than green incentives, we have Latin American resilience.

We dream of a 2030 with less trash and more stories

Thank you all.

Welcome to the eighth art — where, beyond being filmmakers, we try to be good citizens of the world.

Join our Community on WhatsApp

Carbon Calculator(s)

- Simple and easy way to reduce emissions
- Calculate emissions
- It (can) reduce work
- It (can) reduce cost
- Something our students must know and use

We will demonstrate three:
Two online and one based on excel sheet

- PEACHy
- Green Producers Tool
- CarbonClap

Why?

- A easy way to reduce and think sustainable
- To find out what effect your actions have
- It is mandatory to get funding (in some countries)
- For students - to get prepared for the business
 - take actions and have the skills
 - be more attractive
- To save resources and time
- Its good for your health
- It become mandatory for all kinds of business (in Eu)
- They become more and more intuitive and easy to use
 - Takes few hours to calculate a production
- Makes the students to think creative

CREDIT4CE Launches Carbon Footprint Calculator to Drive Green Transition
Date: 28/11/2024
By: CREDIT4CE

We are excited to announce that as a milestone in the CREDIT4CE project, we have successfully developed a user-friendly Carbon Footprint Calculator. It is designed to enable companies, particularly small and medium enterprises (SMEs), to measure their greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, both direct and indirect. By identifying key emission sources, businesses can set actionable sustainability goals, reduce their carbon footprint, and contribute to global decarbonization efforts.

This achievement aligns with our commitment to empowering regions and SMEs with the tools and knowledge to embrace green technologies and accelerate the journey to 'Net Zero'. Start your sustainability journey today with the CREDIT4CE Carbon Footprint Calculator!

You can check the calculator here: <https://carbonfootprint.credit4ce.eu>

For example

- NES - Nordic Ecological Standard
- Based on German, Austrian and British standard
- Mandatory to make a sustainable budget and show measurement - to get funding
- And a report
 - If not you will not get the last installment
- Most Nordic funding institutions have comitted, including broadcasters and regional funds.
- The NES is divided into six overarching categories:
 - general requirements
 - personnel and material transport
 - energy use
 - accommodation and catering
 - use of materials
 - biodiversity
- Mandatory from 2026 (Nordic and Baltic)

NORDIC ECOLOGICAL STANDARD - NES NEWS

Press release: Introducing NES - the Nordic Ecological Standard

September 11th, 2025

<https://www.nfi.no/en/news/introducing-an-ecological-standard-for-sustainable-film-and-tv-production-in-the-nordics>

Introducing an Ecological Standard for Sustainable Film and TV Production in the Nordics

The Nordic Film and TV industry is introducing a common Nordic Ecological Standard (NES) for sustainable production, to be implemented in all the Nordic countries from 2026.

The Nordic Ecological Standard for sustainable film- and TV-production (NES) aims to significantly reduce the environmental footprint of the audiovisual industry in the five Nordic countries.

The national film institutes of Norway, Denmark, Sweden, Finland and Iceland have

Tools

Green Film School Alliance

Notably the top nine in The Hollywood Reporter's 25 Top Film Schools

[Green Production Guide](#)

Environmental Media Association

At EMA, we believe storytelling can change the world for the better. Our goal is to ensure a healthy, sustainable, and secure future for ALL families. Join us on our nonpartisan mission to protect the Earth and ea...

[ema](#) Environmental Media Association

Tools

WHO WE ARE

The Green Film School Alliance (GFSA) is an organization united to integrate industry-level sustainable production practices into film school programs. We commit together to bring a common language, standards, and tools to all institutions. This alliance is built around taking specific actions to reduce the impacts of physical production on the environment, a willingness to share best practices, and a pledge to further sustainable initiatives at all schools.

We are supported by partners at the [Sustainable Entertainment Alliance \(SEA\)](#) and the [Producers Guild of America Green \(PGA Green\)](#). Together they created the Green Production Guide, which continues to be the principal resource for reducing Hollywood's environmental impact by guiding filmmakers and creators at all levels to approach their work in ways that conserve fuel and energy, avoid toxins and pollution, save water, protect nature, and prevent waste. The GFSA, in partnership with SEA, has used the Green Production Guide as a framework to create tools to facilitate students' transition to sustainable production.

Tools

Production Environmental Activity Checklist for Young Filmmakers

PEACHy is a version of the Green Production Guide's industry-standard, best practices Production Environmental Actions Checklist that has been adapted for student productions. Utilizing this worksheet and other resources on the [Green Production Guide website](#) will facilitate producing sustainably. PEACHy is also used to apply for [EMA Green Seal Recognition](#).

[Download PEACHy](#)

sites.google.com/view/greenfilmschoolalliance/production-tools/peachy

Tools

Copy of PEACHY ☆ 📁 ☁

File Edit View Insert Format Data Tools Extensions Help

🔍 ↶ ↷ 🖨️ 📄 75% | \$ % .0_← .00_→ 123 | Calibri | - 11 + | **B** *I* 🔒 A | ⋮ ^

D44 | fx Choose One

	B	C	D	E	F	G
43	DEVELOPMENT & PRE-PRODUCTION					
44	Did you set goals and distribute sustainability memos that communicate your sustainability objectives to cast and crew and were those objectives announced at the first safety meeting and communicated throughout production?	2	Choose One	0	Choose One	0
45	Did you identify the senior person accountable for sustainability (Line Producer, UPM or Production Supervisor) and who is responsible for implementing agreed upon sustainability goals (POC, APOC, or Environmental Representative)?	1	YES NO N/A Choose One	0	Choose One	0
46	Did you work with department heads to incorporate sustainable behaviors (e.g., reusable water bottles and shopping bags) and messaging on screen and with writers to incorporate dialogue or action that portrays or advocates environmental responsibility? If Yes , briefly describe the examples and/or storyline and include scene or episode number(s) if applicable.	4	Choose One	0	Choose One	0

Tools

Green Sets

Learn about greening film sets from the University of North Georgia

Sustainability in Film Teachers Guide
A "quick start" guide for including sustainability in your film curriculum

problem: Climate change and environmental degradation due to human activity, including wasteful practices in the production, consumption, development, streaming, and archiving of film and television.

How is all connected?

solution: Get students engaged in Sustainability with forward-thinking teachers.

The graphic includes a list of environmental issues: Hottest Summer Ever, Wildfires, Refugee Crisis, Severe Weather, Microplastics, Climate Change, Energy consumption, Racism, Cheap labor, Inequity, Fossil Fuels, Range watching, Waste, and Consumerism.

Teachers Guide: Sustainability in Film

A guide to introducing sustainability into your film classroom

Sustainability in Tisch Film

LET'S LEARN ABOUT
FSU FILM SUSTAINABILITY PRACTICES!

The graphic features a recycling bin, a trash bag, and a recycling bin with a camera icon.

Florida State University Film Sustainability Practices

Sustainability successes achieved by Florida State University film students

Carbon Emissions of Film & Television

2022
COST-BENEFIT ANALYSIS OF SUSTAINABLE MEASURES IN STUDENT FILMS

Screenshot

Carbon Calculator: Green Producers Tool

- Online tool
- Used in creative industry
 - Operahouse
 - Theater
 - Music festivals
 - Sports event
 - Film
 - TV
 - Art
- Developed by researcher
- Have all the info in the tool
- It calculates for you
- Since it is online it is updated
 - and it will be developed
- Can make your own templates
- English version

The Green Producers Tool

Do you create or buy productions such as film, events, concerts or festivals? Do you know how much CO2 they emit?

With the Green Producers Tool you can measure emissions and start reducing them!

The Tool is for producers or purchasers of cultural productions and for suppliers in the culture sector's value chains. The tool has six different modules for measuring emissions as of today:

- Film & TV
- Festival
- Performing Arts
- Event
- Sports
- Exhibitions & Artworks

The Tool is dynamic and in development. We are in constant dialogue with the members of the Green Producers Club and will update it according to user input, and technological and scientific development. We are also currently working to tailor a module of the Tool to museums and exhibition production.

Keep Track of Your Emissions

The image shows a smartphone and a laptop displaying the Green Producers Tool interface. The laptop screen shows a dashboard with the following data: Organization: BabuKa, Productions: 54, Emissions: 345 tonnes CO2. Below this, there is a table with columns for 'Productions' and 'Emissions'. One entry is visible: 'Production "Earth..." with 420 emissions and 2480.324 tonnes CO2-eq. The interface also includes search bars, filters, and a 'Show Archived' button.

Green Producers Tool

Productions Ongoing: 35 Emissions: 187.04 tonnes CO2-eq Generate Report

Search title Sort New at bottom

Reset all filters

<p>NM Apnea Film and TV</p> <p>Frode Søbstad Start date: 06.09.2024</p>	<p>Budget / Estimate 1.37 tonnes CO2-eq.</p> <p>25 activities 2 drafts</p>
<p>Onboarding Film and TV</p> <p>GPT Support Start date: 12.09.2024</p>	<p>Budget / Estimate 0.16 tonnes CO2-eq.</p> <p>32 activities 0 drafts</p>
<p>Mal Produksjoner Westerdals Film and TV</p> <p>Frode Søbstad Film og TV Start date: 17.09.2024</p>	<p>Budget / Estimate 0.0 tonnes CO2-eq.</p> <p>1 activities 52 drafts</p>
<p>GPC Mal - Westerdals (referanseprosjekt) Film and TV</p> <p>GPT Support Start date: 23.09.2024</p>	<p>Budget / Estimate 0.59 tonnes CO2-eq.</p> <p>206 activities 0 drafts</p>
<p>Oppdragsfilm - Gruppe 1 Film and TV</p> <p>GPT Support Start date: 30.09.2024</p>	<p>Budget / Estimate 0.36 tonnes CO2-eq.</p> <p>2 activities 0 drafts</p>

← 3 Klasse oktober 2025 Generate Report

0.64
tonnes CO2-eq.

Not grouped bundles

Groups	Kg CO2-eq.	
Phases	644.33	
Pre-production	0.0	
Production	566.85	
Post-production	77.48	
Suppliers	0.0	
Co-Producers	0.0	

Categories	Kg CO2-eq.	
Transport	40.41%	260.35
Food & Beverage	32.59%	209.96
Equipment	12.63%	81.35
Art Department	1.73%	11.14
Energy	0.0%	0.0
Accommodation	3.59%	23.14
Recycling & Waste	0.0%	0.0
Costumes	7.41%	47.72
Props	0.03%	0.2

Activities 42 Emissions: 566.85 kg CO2-eq Generate Report

Select Filters

Production	566.85 Kg CO2-eq.
Technical Equipment	292.87 Kg CO2-eq.
Set Design & Scenography	3.34 Kg CO2-eq.
Props	0.0 Kg CO2-eq.
Costumes & Make-up	47.72 Kg CO2-eq.
Food & Beverage	0.0 Kg CO2-eq.
Travel	222.92 Kg CO2-eq.
Accommodation	0.0 Kg CO2-eq.
Energy	0.0 Kg CO2-eq.
Resource Management	0.0 Kg CO2-eq.

New activity

Green Producers Tool

← Add a title for your activity/ies here Send Bundle

● Phases / Production / Costumes & Make-up [Edit Groups](#)

+ Add Activity

Large costume - several layers	0.08 Kg CO2-eq.	⋮
Large costume - several layers	1.83 Kg CO2-eq.	⋮
Medium costume - full body	45.81 Kg CO2-eq.	⋮

Total Emissions [Add Multiplier](#)
47.72 Kg CO2-eq.

Made by Frode Søbstad on October 13, 2025

Costumes / Costume garments

Type *
Medium costume - full body

Main material *
Cotton (150 g/m2)

Origin *
Purchased new / Produced new

Quantity *
2

Activity date *
01.12.2025

Description

Tags

Make a Draft

Draft activities are excluded from the emission totals. This status should be used for activities that are not yet finalized.

← Add a title for your activity/ies here Send Bundle

• Phases / Production / Travel Edit Groups

+ Add Activity

Bus	69.85 Kg CO2-eq.	⋮
Car	153.07 Kg CO2-eq.	⋮
Total Emissions	Add Multiplier	
222.92 Kg CO2-eq.		

Made by Frode Søbstad on October 23, 2025
Transport / Transport of people

Means of transport *
Bus

Type *
Public

Fuel *
Fossil Fuel

Calculate Route Enter Distance

Starting point *
Av. Ignacio L Vallarta 3298, Vallarta Nte., 44690 Gua

Destination *
Puerto Vallarta, Jalisco, Mexico

+ Add Destination

Distance (km)
297.87 Reset Route

Return trip

Number of persons *
1

Activity date *
23.10.2025 📅

Save and Close

Add More Activities

- + Add Content block
- Climate accounting in Gre...
- Production information
- Total emissions based on t...
- Total emissions based on t...**
- Total emissions per Activit...
- Total emissions per Year
- Total emissions per Month
- Transport
- Food & Beverage
- Equipment
- Costumes
- Accommodation
- Art Department
- Scenography
- Props
- What is Green Producers T...

Production: 3 Klasse oktober 2025

Total emissions per Activity Category

Productions: 3 Klasse oktober 2025

Total 37 activities **643.42** kg CO2-eq.

Activity categories	%	kg CO2-eq.
---------------------	---	------------

> Transport	40.46%	260.35
-------------	--------	--------

Carbon Calculator: CarbonClap

carbonclap.ecoprod.com

MY PROJECTS

Access your projects and their carbon footprints, and create new projects.

NEW PROJECT +

Your projects	Production companies	Label	CSR+	Created on	Updated on	Report type	Status	Footprint	Actions
Title of the project Feature film EXERCICE PROJECT	My Porudciton Company	-	-	1/7/25	1/7/25	Projected	Completed	21 tCO2e	
My Project 2025 Feature film EXERCICE PROJECT	My Best Production Company	-	-	1/6/25	2/18/25	Projected	Open	9 tCO2e	
				1/6/25	1/6/25	Final	Open	0 tCO2e	
test Fictional short film EXERCICE PROJECT	Test	-	-	12/11/24	12/11/24	Projected	Open	0 tCO2e	
OMDM				2/19/24	3/27/24	Projected	Completed	41 tCO2e	

Carbon Calculator: CarbonClap

carbonclap.ecoprod.com

Production	Production facilities Computer equipment Insurance and services	0 tCO ₂ e	EDIT
Filming locations	Indoor filming locations Outdoor filming locations	0 tCO ₂ e	EDIT
Set design	Workplaces Set creation Film vehicles Special effects and stunts	0 tCO ₂ e	EDIT
Hair Makeup Costumes	Workplaces Costumes and clothes Makeup Hair	0 tCO ₂ e	EDIT
Transport	Road transport Air transport Rail transport Sea transport Group travel	0 tCO ₂ e	EDIT
Production logistics	Meals Craft Services Hosting Waste	0 tCO ₂ e	EDIT
Technical production means	Shooting, grip, lighting and sound Special technical equipment Production control room Production trailer Generator and portable power station	0 tCO ₂ e	EDIT
Post-production	Post-production activities Digital archive	0 tCO ₂ e	EDIT

carbonclap.ecoprod.com

Carbon Calculator: EcoProd

carbonclap.ecoprod.com

Indoor filming location

Filming location name *

Production phase(s) * ?

Preproduction

Shooting

Filming location type * ?

Filming location country *

Building capital asset and energy

Filming location surface area * ?

 m2

Ancillary spaces (dressing rooms, HMC, etc.) surface area * ?

 m2

Is the building less than 30 years old? * ?

Number of days this location is used

 day

Do you use the grid energy of this location for the filming and the ancillary spaces? *

Carbon Calculator: EcoProd

carbonclap.ecoprod.com

Some Classroom Examples

Green Storytelling

- Require or encourage students to make films that have the environment and/or our relationship to nature as **the main theme**: this can be in any genre.
- Give assignments focussing on ecology (either obligatory or as one of different options) and use the occasion to lecture on more green ways to make films.

Screenwriting exercise 1: let the students pick one scene and rewrite choices to reduce environmental load (e.g., day-for-night instead of night exteriors, consolidate locations, public space over distant/private).

Screenwriting exercise 2: let the students select a 1–2 page scene from an existing script and highlight lines that imply high-carbon settings/props. Propose a same-beat alternative in the margin.

Green Producing

Introduce a **Green calculator tool**: teach students and encourage them to use a carbon emission budget for their productions.

- For example: adjust call-sheets for student productions to include the distances between home or school and the set.
 - Replace printed call sheets, shot lists, scripts with a single digital folder + QR code on set.
- + Have a sustainability coordinator on set...

Encourage the use of **smartphones** to shoot student films instead of big cameras (especially in the case of documentary).

Exercise in Cinematography: make the students shoot a scene with energy-intense-lights vs. low-energy-lights and have them submit an energy table on how much was spent or saved and describe the CO₂-impact.

Green Films: Reuse, Recycle, Reduce...

- This is a **general principle** that can be applied to the costume department, for building sets etc. (see also the examples from yesterday).
- Try to build a **local prop and costume department** in the school with recycled and recovered items that can be reused: this can be done by dump diving and scavenging (flea markets, thrift stores, ...).

In the long run also imply **material reclamation** (e-waste is a good example).

- **Production Design:** add a category to the design board that states where objects, costumes etc. came from and where they will go next.

Green Films: Reuse, Recycle, Reduce...

- Let the students make **stop motion animation films** with used materials and (re-)used) puppets.
 - Have students **recycle and reuse images itself** to make found-footage films (documentary and experimental films; but is also applicable in dream scenes, flash-backs, sci-fi...).
- + **Introduce a “Certified Green Course” label for all courses that qualify.**

Manifesto

1. As SCS we embrace the responsibility of empowering our educational communities towards a creative culture committed to the ecological future of the planet.
2. We see ourselves as agents of change, and action is needed, urgent... but also doable: see our 20 ideas and our call to action today.
3. This is a call for **collective** action of the CILECT community: to apply the 20 ideas, and to share learnings, experiences and strategies among all members.
4. We see this as an act of hope inspired by the urgency of the moment and the belief that audiovisual creation can be a catalyst for transformation.
5. Our vision for the future is to reduce our impact on the environment and cultivate a creative environment that promotes peace – peace that results from environmental stewardship, thoughtful cooperation, and mutual learning.

6. We hope to transform the way we see ourselves and the world with ethics: to affirm our commitment to life, climate justice, and an education that inspires today and for generations to come.

7. We encourage everyone to tell stories that matter: each story told has the power to transform consciousness, open dialogue, and mobilize society.

8. We accept the social responsibility to recognize the larger impact of our practices: every film shoot involves communities, territories, resources, people and cultures.

9. We strive for more sustainability on the set and beyond, and to ensure that production processes respect cultural diversity, promote gender equity, protect labor rights, and safeguard the dignity of all individuals involved.

10. May this manifesto not only be a declaration, but also a living commitment. May our schools, our students, and our communities find in cinema and audiovisual media a space to imagine fairer, more humane, and more sustainable futures.

CILECT Congress 2025 - Guadalajara